

**FAILURE MECHANISMS IN FILLED
EPOXY RESINS**

W.J. Cantwell and A.C. Roulin-Moloney.
Laboratoire de Polymères
Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne
CH-1007 Lausanne
Switzerland

ABSTRACT

The effects of time, temperature and loading conditions on the fracture surface morphologies in filled epoxy resins are discussed and related to the mechanisms of fracture in these materials. The microstructure is found to be a function of crack velocity, low velocities being characterised by resin-particle debonding whereas, at high velocities the particles remain well bonded to the matrix. The transition is, however, a function of the test temperature.

INTRODUCTION

Highly crosslinked polymers such as epoxy resins are well suited for a wide range of applications such as matrices in reinforced composites, adhesives in the aerospace industry and as resins for insulating materials used in the power industry. As a result of these demands,

much work has been undertaken in an attempt to characterise the mechanics of deformation and fracture in these materials over the wide range of loading conditions and environments likely to be encountered in operational service. However, much of this work gives the appearance of being ad-hoc in nature and in spite of the fact that many parameters have been varied a deeper understanding of the basic mechanisms still remains a pressing requirement.

There is considerable interest in the potential of multi-phase systems such as particulate-filled resins where increases in toughness can be achieved without any loss in tensile or flexural strength. Here too, a thorough understanding of the mechanisms responsible for fracture has not yet been fully achieved. The work presented here describes some of the findings of a research project inaugurated to examine and explain the mechanisms involved in the fracture of a silica-filled epoxy resin under a variety of test conditions. Since short term tests do not fully represent those encountered in operational service, an extensive programme of creep tests encompassing a wide range of temperatures has been undertaken. With the aid of both scanning electron and optical microscopes, attention has been given to identifying and explaining those features and regions apparent on the fracture surface of this filled epoxy resin with the aim of developing new systems with enhanced static fatigue capability.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The resin used in this investigation was a hydantoin based epoxy resin (type XB 2900) cured by a formulated anhydride hardener (HY 925). Silica particles of mean size of approximately 50 μm were incorporated to give a volume fraction of 40%. In order to avoid machining, the resin was generally cured in individual pre-heated moulds. The curing was carried out in accordance with the manufacturers instructions, that is, a gelation time of 4 hours at 80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ followed by 16 hours at 130 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. This procedure yielded a uniform distribution of particles and a material of glass transition temperature of 120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

In order to reproduce the loading conditions likely to be encountered in operational service a variety of specimen geometries have been considered. These include tensile tests using dumb-bell samples of circular cross-section and fracture mechanics specimens such as double torsion and single edge notch. Since many of these geometries are inherently unstable the determination of crack velocity by visual observation was impossible. In cases where the geometry permitted, a graphite gauge technique was employed enabling crack velocities up to many hundreds of metres per second to be determined accurately. The method has been described in detail in reference 1. It consists of applying a thin layer of graphite to the specimen bounded

by two silver electrodes along the presumed path of the crack. The change in the inverse of resistance with time enables the crack position, and hence the crack velocity, to be determined. The output from the graphite gauge is fed into a data logger (capable of enregistering data points up to each 500 ns) and this is in turn coupled to a minicomputer.

Short term tensile tests were conducted using the dumb-bell geometry at four temperatures 23°C, 50°C, 85°C and 105°C, these lower three temperatures represent the range of conditions likely to be found in operational service of electrical insulators.

Long term tests were also undertaken using the dumb-bell specimen. Loading was effected by means of a system of bars and levers which augmented the static load by a factor of 10, enabling high stresses to be achieved. Testing was conducted at four load levels namely; 20%, 40%, 60% and 80% of the ultimate strength as determined from the short term tests. The specimens were supported in four ovens each of which were capable of accommodating between 7 and 15 independent tests. As before, four test temperatures were considered, 23°C, 50°C, 85°C and 105°C, permitting comparisons to be made between short and long term tests. During the course of the testing, the deformation of the specimen was monitored using by means of a strain gauge bonded to the test length. The output was fed into a HBM data logger which was in turn coupled to a minicomputer for assessment and subsequent storage of the strain measurements. This system was capable of handling up to 60 separate channels of information once every 2 seconds, permitting the complete deformation and failure history of each of the specimens to be recorded accurately.

The resulting fracture surfaces were examined using a low power Olympus optical microscope and a Cambridge Instruments S100 scanning electron microscope.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 gives a schematic diagram of the fracture surface of tensile specimen in a filled epoxy resin. A cursory examination of these specimens highlighted four zones, the size and magnitude of which varied with the loading conditions and test temperature as shown in the optical micrographs given in Figure 2. Fracture can sometimes be linked to the presence of a flaw or defect which may derive from foreign bodies incorporated during specimen preparation, from resin-rich areas or mould lines, large particles or poorly bonded particles. The initiation point is surrounded by a region in which the particles are debonded from the matrix. The size of this debonded region was found to increase rapidly with increasing temperature and reducing load (hence, increased time to failure). The size of this debonded area was measured by gold coating the specimens which highlighted this region, and then observed using an optical microscope.

Beyond the debonded region is a smooth zone in which the particles are well-bonded to the surrounding matrix. Here again, the size of this zone was dictated by the loading conditions and test temperature and in certain cases can occupy a large percentage of the fracture surface.

The remainder of the fracture surface exhibits a rough, strongly three-dimensional form indicative of rapid crack propagation and extensive crack branching. The extent of such crack branching was clearly determined by the conditions of test, being more severe in those specimens tested for short times at lower temperatures. The specimen tested in a short term test exhibits a small smooth zone with the majority of the fracture surface being occupied by the rough region where the effect of crack branching is clearly evident. With reducing load, the size of the smooth zone increases while the degree of crack branching reduces.

Each of these three latter zones will be discussed in more detail:

The Debonded Zone

The size of the debonded region surrounding the point of initiation is of particular interest as its size appears to be a crucial parameter in controlling the static fatigue lifetime of these materials. The appearance of such debonded regions suggested that this mechanism was linked to some form of slow, sub-critical crack growth. In order to examine this possibility in more detail, a series of double torsion tests were conducted over a temperature range of 23°C to 105°C. The advantage of such a test lies in the fact that the double torsion geometry is essentially stable enabling crack velocities as low as 10^{-6} m/s to be achieved quite easily. The fracture surfaces were examined in the SEM to determine whether the particles were bonded or debonded from the matrix. The information from this series of tests is presented in graphical form in Figure 3 where the variation of the debonding threshold is determined as a function of test temperature. On examining this curve, it is clear that particle-matrix separation can occur at all temperatures considered. However, the velocity at which debonding begins is strongly temperature dependent; at 105°C being apparent over the whole span of crack velocities. In order to analyse further the causes and resulting effects of particle debonding, a fracture mechanics type of analysis was conducted where the stress at failure σ_f is related to the debonded zone size (a) by the relationship:

$$K_{IC} = \sigma_f Y \sqrt{a}$$

where K_{IC} is the fracture toughness and Y is a geometric factor taken here as the value for an edge notch in an infinitely wide sheet. Figure 4 shows that the data complies reasonably well

with the trends predicted by LEFM and a value for the fracture toughness of $2.29 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ was determined by a curve fitting procedure. This value is in quite good agreement with the value determined previously for this material (2).

The evidence presented above substantiates the suggestion that the debonded zone represents the region where the crack grows slowly and sub-critically. It is reasonable to assume, therefore, that this region will be critical in determining the static fatigue resistance of such a composite component.

The Smooth Zone

The smooth zone is a relatively flat, featureless region surrounding the initiation and debonded zone whose size increases rapidly with increasing test temperature and decreasing applied load. Physically determining the crack velocity in this region is impossible since the geometry of the dumb-bell specimen is not conducive to the use of the graphite gauge. Instead, testing was conducted on the single edge notch geometry in which the crack velocity can be readily determined. In Figure 5 the fracture surface of a single edge notch specimen is given. Closer examination of the figure highlights the pre-crack on the immediate left of the specimen (0.25 mm) followed by a smooth region similar in appearance to that noted in the previous dumb-bell specimens. Further away from the point of fracture initiation the surface becomes very rough and three-dimensional with many large whitened features indicative of crack branching. The corresponding velocity profile is also given in Figure 5. The sensibility and flexibility of the data recorder permits crack velocities to be determined very accurately at any point. A comparison of the fractographic features and the velocity profile indicates that over the smooth zone the crack is continuously accelerating and only when it achieves its maximum value (800 m/s) does the fracture surface exhibit the previously discussed roughness. This shows, therefore, that the smooth region in this filled epoxy corresponds to the region of crack acceleration in which the excess energy is dissipated by driving the crack faster.

The Rough Region

The rough zone has a whitened, three-dimensional appearance as shown in Figure 2. Examination of Figure 5 shows that this fracture surface morphology occurs when the crack reaches its terminal velocity (800 m/s for this material). Here, the excess energy is dissipated by crack branching. The extent of branching decreases with reducing load (or increased time to failure) and by increasing the test temperature.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The fracture surfaces of the silica filled epoxy resin can be characterized by four regions namely, (i) defect (although not always in evidence), (ii) a debonded region, (iii) a smooth zone and (iv) a rough zone.
2. The debonded region represents the zone of sub-critical crack growth, the development of which controls the static fatigue lifetime.
3. The smooth zone corresponds to the area over which the crack is accelerating. Here it is seems that the excess energy is dissipated in driving the crack faster.
4. The rough region occurs when the crack velocity has attained its limiting value, here the excess stored elastic energy is dissipated in creating new fracture surfaces.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to thank Professor H.H. Kausch for his continued support and encouragement and Brown Boveri and Cie and the Commission pour l'Encouragement de la Recherche Scientifique for the financial assistance which made this project possible. They would also like to thank Brian Senior and the Institut Interdepartmental de Microscopie (EPFL) for much help with scanning electron microscopy, Jean-Luc Roulin for technical assistance and T. Kaiser, J.W. Smith, H.R. Beer and A. Demarmels (BBC) for helpful suggestions and discussions.

REFERENCES

1. Stalder B., Béguelin Ph. and Kausch H.H., Int. J. Fracture, (1983) 22 R47.
2. Beer H-R., Kaiser T., Moloney A.C. and Kausch H.H., J. Mater. Sci., (1986) 21 3661.

Figure 1. Regions on the fracture surface in a filled epoxy resin.

3.467

Strength test

80% ultimate

60% ultimate

Figure 2. The effect of loading conditions on the fracture surface morphology.

Figure 3. The effect of crack velocity on particle-matrix debonding.

● bonded □ partially debonded ○ debonded

Figure 4. Fracture mechanics correlation between tests on dumb-bell specimens and single edge notch tests.

○ SEN tests at 23°C
 ▲ SEN tests at 85°C ● strength and creep tests at 85°C

Figure 5. The variation of crack velocity across a single edge notch sample.